

**EFFECTS OF DUMPSITE ON GROUNDWATER AT IWOROKO-EKITI,
EKITI STATE**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this project work was carried out by MOGBOYINOLA ADEBISI AYOMIDE, matric number 178538063 in the Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God through whom I find mercy upon the land of EKSU.
And to my wonderful parents, Mr and Mrs MOGBOYINOLA for their prayers, labour and love.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I give glory to GOD the giver of life, for his goodness and mercy that endures over me throughout my years of study. I appreciate him for standing by me all through situations from the beginning to the end, may His name be exalted forever, Amen.

To my amiable and ever respected supervisor, **PROF. J. O. ARIBISALA** for his availability all through the implementation of this project, I pray God is your eternal reward in Jesus name, Amen.

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ABSTRACT

The quality of groundwater is the cumulative result of various processes and reactions that have impacted the water through its journey, from its initial formation through atmospheric condensation to its eventual extraction from a well. Groundwater pollution which is manmade is much worse than natural pollution as it eventually renders water less suitable for use than its original state. The manmade pollution or waste used in this project is solid waste. Solid waste is the unwanted or useless solid materials generated from combined residential, industrial and commercial activities in a given area. This project was carried out in order to know the effect of a dumpsite on groundwater through the following tests; pH, temperature, alkalinity, turbidity, colour, odour, appearance, etc and how to effectively collect and manage refuse dumps to prevent contamination of groundwater sources, ensuring safe and clean water for drinking and domestic use.

Physical, chemical and bacteriological tests were carried out on the groundwater near and far from the selected dumpsite in Iworoko-Ekiti area. Two samples were taken from the wells near and far from the dumpsite.

Results of physical and chemical tests show that the water has colour, taste and odour. The average temperature and pH values are 26.05°C and 5.81 respectively. The conductivity values are 719 μ s/cm and 711 μ s/cm. Hardness ranges are relatively soft and the Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) are 691mg/L and 687mg/L. Bacteriological tests revealed that the waters from the study area are highly contaminated. However, the chemical constituents of the water samples fall within the W.H.O. permissible limits.

The result on the composition of the waste shows that the dumpsite consists of 50% of plastic, 20% of food waste, 25% of paper and 5% of metallic waste.

Conclusion on the project shows that the total coliform and E coli of the well water samples exceeds the W.H.O. standard limit. The pH of the well water samples is slightly acidic and does not fall between W.H.O. standard limit for drinking water. The total hardness, total solid and other chemical parameters of the water samples from the study are within W.H.O. acceptable limit and appearance, colour, taste and odour of the well water samples are all objectionable.

Recommendation given is that regular laboratory tests should be conducted on water samples, wells in the selected area should be treated against acidity with lime and treated against E coli with chlorine and the dumpsite should be properly disposed.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The disposal of waste in dumpsites has become a pressing environmental concern, with significant implications for groundwater quality. Groundwater is a vital source of freshwater, providing drinking water for millions of people worldwide. However, the proximity of dumpsites to groundwater sources poses a significant threat to its quality and safety. The leachate from dumpsites can seep into the soil and contaminate the groundwater, leading to the presence of harmful pollutants, such as heavy metals, pesticides, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). This contamination can have devastating effects on human health, the environment, and the ecosystem as a whole. In this context, it is essential to investigate the effects of dumpsites on groundwater quality, identify the potential health risks, and develop effective strategies for mitigating this problem. By understanding the impact of dumpsites on groundwater quality, we can work towards ensuring a safer and more sustainable future for generations to come.

1.1 Solid waste (dumpsite)

Solid waste is the unwanted or useless solid materials generated from combined residential, industrial, and commercial activities in a given area. It may be categorized according to its origin (domestic, industrial, commercial), according to its contents (organic material, glass, metals, plastic paper, etc) or according to hazard potential (toxic, non toxic etc), (Morris, 1751). Furthermore, solid waste can be defined as the heterogeneous mass throw-away from residences and commercial activities as well as the more heterogeneous accumulation of single industrial activities (Aribisala, 1997).

Solid wastes are classified basically by origin of generation with a view of obtaining workable and efficient methods of storage, collection, treatment and disposals. Primarily, solid wastes are classified as garbage, ashes and rubbish. Garbage is solid to include the organic matter that results from preparation and consumption of foods. It could be said to be materials that are putrescible i.e decomposable materials. Ashes are the residues that result after cooking and heating processes. Rubbish is that class that embrace most solid waste which are not included in the other two classes. It contains non-putrescible materials i.e non decomposable materials and this include combustibles such as paper, rags, wood, leaves and weeds or non-combustibles such as glass, mortal and concrete materials. A more comprehensive classification is given as

- Garbage
- Rubbish
- Ashes
- Street refuse
- Dead Animals
- Abandoned vehicles
- Industrial wastes
- Demolition waste

- Construction wastes
- Special waste
- Sewage treatment residue
- Agricultural waste.

FIG. 1.1 Percentage by weight composition of waste in Ado-Ekiti

Source: Aribisala, 2004

1.2 Groundwater

Groundwater is the water present beneath Earth's surface in rock and soil_pore_spaces and in the fractures of rock-formations. A unit of rock or an unconsolidated deposit is called an aquifer when it can yield a usable quantity of water. The depth at which soil pore spaces or fractures and voids in rock become completely saturated with water is called the water_table. Groundwater is recharged from the surface; it may discharge from the surface naturally at springs and seeps, and can form oases or wetlands. Groundwater is also often withdrawn for agricultural, municipal, and industrial use by constructing and operating extraction wells. The study of the distribution and movement of groundwater is hydrogeology, also called groundwater hydrology.

1.3 Statement of the research problem

The proximity of dumpsites to groundwater sources poses a significant threat to the quality and safety of the water supply. Leachate from the dumpsite can contaminate the groundwater, leading to the presence of harmful pollutants, such as heavy metals, pesticides, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). This can have devastating effects on human health, including increased risk of cancer, neurological damage, and other serious health problems. Furthermore, the contamination of groundwater can also affect the local ecosystem, causing harm to plants, animals, and microorganisms that rely on the water supply. therefore, it is essential to investigate the impact of dumpsites on groundwater quality and develop effective strategies for mitigating

this problem. Also, the lack of effective waste management strategies and infrastructure in many areas has resulted in significant environmental, economic, and social impacts, highlighting the need for sustainable solutions to address the solid waste crisis.

1.4 Aims

This research was carried out with a view of accessing the effect of leachates from a dumpsite on the groundwater, in order to achieve this aim, the chemical, physical and bacteriological tests were compared with the World Health Organization (2006) standard for drinking water with the motive of predicting their level of pollution and/or contamination or as the case may be.

1.5 Objectives

- To determine waste composition at dump site.
- To carry out laboratory tests of well water around the dumpsite.
- To determine the impact of solid waste on groundwater.

1.6 Significance of study

Groundwater pollution occurs as a result of the release of pollutants into natural groundwater reservoirs known as aquifers. Once the pollutants released find their way into groundwater, they cause contamination. Contaminated groundwater has detrimental effects on human health. In areas where dumpsites are not properly managed, they may contaminate the water source. The waste may contain hepatitis-causing bacteria that may lead to irreversible damage to the liver.

Also, it may cause dysentery, which leads to severe diarrhea, dehydration, and, in some cases, death. Drinking water from such a source may lead to serious health effects. So, the significance of this study is to know the best way to avoid dumping of solid waste affecting the groundwater, which is polluted by the refuse dumped around it. In addition, this project will educate the public on the consequences or problems of improper deposition of waste around where wells are situated, how the waste can be managed or properly disposed and how the water contaminated can be treated to give a potable drinking water.

1.7 Scope and limitations

The scope of this project is to study the effects of solid waste on groundwater of selected wells at Iworoko-Ekiti, to know the composition of the waste at dumpsite. Knowing the composition at the dumpsite helps us to know the kind of pollution expected. To know how the dumpsite can be properly managed in the area, whether to be burnt or taken to a safer location. To know the extent of the contamination in the wells and the treatment required for the water to be potable.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The management of solid waste in the rural/urban areas of Ekiti state requires immediate planning before it assumes a hazardous state. Before the creation of Ekiti state, there has not been any organized system of solid waste disposal by the state government. The problems of managing the disposal of solid waste has started in many of our urban towns, within the state, and to plan for effective disposal, collection and processing of solid waste, you must understand the various composition of the waste collected for disposal.

Solid waste was classified by the American public works department as following: household, garbage and rubbish, residential ashes, commercial refuse, construction and demolition debris, street cleaning and maintenance refuse, dead animal as agricultural waste and special waste.

The influx of people into the new state capital and its environment will continue for sometimes, it will consequently generate the following problems of waste management in Ekiti state;

1. The empty land previously used as refuse dump area is fast disappearing as residential and commercial buildings are erected on them.
2. Bushes for dumping refuse is reducing as lands are purchased and houses are built on them, thereby making the distance where refuse could be dumped to be farther away from the people and also reducing the land space for such purpose.
3. More solid waste will be generated by the populace as a result of increase in the population

The composition and density of solid waste generated in a locality depends largely on the population size of the area involved and the degree of the commercial, domestic and industrial activities going on in the area. Standard of living of the resident taken the largest role in the composition and density of waste generated.

More light is also shed on the average analysis of waste and change, which occur in term of high diversity, low density in commercial areas, for example, Lagos area or Ibadan. In Lagos, vegetable or organic matters forms the largest percentage of their domestic refuse generated.

Despite all the effort made by Nigeria researchers and subsequently by the states and federal government to find solution to the waste problem in our urban centres, the conclusion each observer draw is that there is no improvement being made in collection and disposal of waste throughout the country (Adesunloro, 1997). This is because the solid waste management process has always been examined and planned in piece meal manner instead of regarding it as a system and with numerous and significant operations which influence one another. The study is therefore an attempt to contribute to the literature on solid waste management in Nigeria cities with reference to Ekiti state.

In Nigeria, the idea of systematic collection, transportation and disposal of refuse is relatively new. It is only in the past decades that people are aware of the waste problems. But up till now people are adamant to correction. For example, during raining season, people normally dumped their waste into the running water caused by the rain and those discharge waste causes blockages in the culverts and drainages, which normally result to flooding of highways. But if people follow the instruction of waste management they cannot dump waste anyhow anywhere.

In the rural areas where they are ignorant of these new disposal system (waste collection methods), government has to educate them through television programs, radio programs and newspaper. This will help to adopt and follow the solid waste disposal system, it also protect our environment from heaps of solid waste and blocking of drainage with solid waste during raining season.

2.1 Waste storage

When solid wastes are generated in household, commercial and industrial and on the street, they are stored before they are being collected and disposed to the normal site. Waste storage may be divided into two basic categories; (i) separate unit storage and (ii) communal storage (Krieth et al, 2002). In Nigeria, waste storage is not standardized. Wastes are generally stored in non-standardized containers which range from temporary containers such as cardboard cartoons, plastic bags, baskets and crate; these are used particularly in the low-income household unit. Most of the plastic or metal bins used are with or without lids. The wastes are therefore exposed to the effects of hot climates where decomposition occurs rapidly with the resultant production of leachate, poisonous and noxious gases.

The size of the containers depends on the density of wastes being disposed and length of storage with respect to the frequency of collection. The climate of the urban area and the open space of the individual premises upon which waste is being stored affect collection frequency. Also, the hotter the area the more frequent collection of waste reduced the odour, insect breeding and vector area.

2.2 Waste collection

Waste collection involves the transportation of waste from storage points to disposal sites. There are three basic types of collection techniques, (i) those that rely on humans, (ii) those that rely on animals and (iii) those that rely on machines. In the three techniques adopted in the collection of wastes, the motorized collection is the most expensive and the most efficient, that can improve collection productivity, if the government of Ekiti can afford to finance it, everywhere will be free of waste in the urban area and also, the money spend on medical will be reduced.

2.3 Waste disposal

The indiscriminate dumping of waste into land, river and drains is probably the oldest method of disposal by man, which is most commonly used in Ekiti state. But in the modern world, there are many other methods of disposing waste which includes the following;

I. Sanity land filling

- II. Incineration
- III. Composition
- IV. Pulverization
- V. Pyrolysis (Tchobanoglous et al, 1998)

Waste may be put to some useful purpose or it may be dumped. Re-use may occur at the place where the waste comes from, as when goat feed on banana peels, or an empty tin can be used as a drinking cup. Also, plastic rubber or slipper or motor parts that has been disposed can still be reused. Even when treatment is intensive, as in a modern refuse incinerator, there is a residue, which has to be put somewhere. Fortunately, as we see, dumping when properly controlled or managed can achieve a useful purpose by recycling.

2.4 Effect of waste on water (Groundwater)

The leachate produced by waste disposal sites contains a large amount of substances which are likely to contaminate ground water. The impact of such sites upon ground water can be judged by monitoring the concentration of potential contaminants at a number of specific monitoring points. The effects of dumping activity on ground water appeared most clearly as high concentrations of total dissolved solids, electrical conductivity, total hardness, chlorides, chemical oxygen demand, nitrates and sulphates. Study clearly indicates that landfills in densely populated cities should have the ground water monitored on regular basis. Furthermore, ground water in and around the landfill sites shall not be used for drinking purposes unless it meets specific standards.

The following are the biological, physical and chemical events that lead to occurrence of leachate;

- i. Biological decay of organic materials.
- ii. Chemical oxidation of waste materials.
- iii. Escape of the gases from the fill.
- iv. Dissolving leachate moving through the fill
- v. Movement of dissolved material through concentration gradients and osmosis.

Since leachate from organic wastes can be highly polluting, the geological suitability of a proposed site is one of the basic matters of resolution.

2.5 Environmental and social constraints

Planning a water treatment and saving it from diverse effects caused by refuse require an understanding of water related disease (Savaders and Warford, 1976). Water related diseases are grouped into four;

- i The faecal oral disease (often water borne disease) is transmitted by contaminated water which is taken in by food. The infections in this group are diarrhoea and dysentery, cholera, typhoid, rotavirus diarrhoea, paratyphoid.
- ii Water washed disease may be significantly reduced by improved personal hygiene for which sufficient water for personal use is essentially infection free.
- iii Water based diseases are caused by parasitic organism which develop in water snail and can infect people who came in direct contact with water. They can be prevented by;
 - Improved sanitation,
 - By the control of water snails and
 - By the provision of a safe and adequate water supply.

The infection in this group are guinea worm, schistosomiasis.

iv Water related insect vector is caused by insect biting near water and bleeding in water. The infections in this group are sleeping sickness, yellow fever, malaria, river blindness, filariasis.

TABLE: 2.1 shows the modes of transmission and their prevention strategy

S/N	TRANSMISSION MECHANISM	PREVENTION STRATEGY
1	Water-borne	Improved quality of drinking water prevent casual use of unimproved source
2	Water-washed	Increase water quality used and improve hygiene
3	Water-based	Decreased hygiene decrease need for contact with infected water
4	Water related vector	Improved surface water management and destroy breeding site of insect

SOURCE: Adapted from cairn cross et al., (1983).

The following health benefits of water treatment project depends on number of environmental and behavioural factors which should be considered in the planning and treatment process;

- a) Water quality for personal hygiene, such as hand washing, bathing and washing of dishes.
- b) Water quality, through source protection and water treatment
- c) Accessibility of safe water
- d) Adequate sanitation
- e) Health education program explaining the benefit of improved water supply and to motivate them to participate in the planning operation and financing of the project.

2.6 System of solid waste management

The term solid waste management mainly refers to the complete process of collecting, treating and disposing of solid waste. In the waste management process, the wastes are collected from different sources and are disposed of. This process includes collection, transportation, treatment, analysis and disposal of waste. It needs to be monitored so that strict regulations and guidelines are followed.

Effective solid waste management requires a comprehensive approach that considers the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), waste minimization, and sustainable practices throughout the waste management hierarchy.

Some examples of solid waste management systems include integrated waste management systems (IWMS), zero waste systems, pay-as-you-throw systems, waste-to-energy systems, and recycling and composting programs.

2.7 Method of waste collection

The methods of solid waste collection such as domestic and commercial wastes to the disposal sites are as follow:

- a) Door to door collection services
- b) Street or close collection services
- c) House to house collection services

2.7.1 Door to door collection service

Door to door collection method is a kind of collection method whereby waste like paper, polythene, organic waste materials, tins etc., can be collected from household to household. This method cannot be practice in any part of Ekiti state because the whole state did not have a well-arranged layout and also there is no capital to support the system.

Advantages

- (a) The storage and collection of waste from the producing source is very easy and the sorting out of waste component from the collection is also easy.

(b) It also creates capital for the state by selling the non organic such as paper, tins, polythene etc to manufacturers for recycling.

Disadvantages

(a) Not all the occupants of the houses will be met at home during the collection.

(b) It is also very expensive to practice in this kind of our community.

2.7.2 Street or close collection services

In this kind of system, a very large open waste storage containers will be placed at different strategic locations in streets and when the storage containers are filled, the waste container will be hauled and transport it to land fill site, emptied the container and return them to their original location. This type of collection has been practiced in Lagos from early 70s to late 80s. This system is suitable in Ado-Ekiti, since there is no proper lay out for buildings.

Advantages

- a) Waste can be disposed, emptied into the containers at any time of the day
- b) It does not involve paying of fee before the disposal of waste into the waste storage containers.
- c) It reduced the dumping of refuse at unlawful area.

2.7.3 House to house collection services

This is a system that involves the collection of solid waste with vehicles. This is a system that can work very well in all parts of Ekiti state. In the three techniques adapted in the collection of solid waste, the House-to-House is the most expensive and efficient one that can improve collection and transportation of solid wastes. If the Ado Local Government Authority can afford to finance it, everywhere will be free of waste in urban centres and the rural areas.

2.8 Method of waste disposal

Increase in population brings a lot of waste especially the use of nylon bags, leaves, sachet water, bread nylon etc, are seen littering the streets in Ekiti State like Ado-Ekiti, Aramoko-Ekiti, Ifaki-Ekiti, Ido-Ekiti etc., in other to make our environment free of solid waste disposal, one of the following methods of solid waste disposal must be embarked on. The methods are as follows:

2.8.1 Sanitary landfill

Sanitary land fill is the engineering method of controlling solid waste disposal on the upper layer of the earth's mantles. Well compacted with the earth moving machine to the smallest practice thickness and covering the compacted layer with the soil at each working day in a manner that protect our immediate environment from sort of pollution. Compaction and covering of refuse help in the following ways:

- a) It limits the odour emission

- b) It prevents the emergence of fly lava
- c) It prevents the log refuse being blowing away by wind
- d) It provides good condition for the biological degradation of organic matter in the tip
- e) It prevents the breeding of flies.

The factors to be considered before the sanitary land fill system takes off are:

- a) Site location
- b) Incineration
- c) Compositing
- d) Recycling (Tchobanoglous et al, 1998)

2.8.2 Landfill methods and operations

To use the available area locate for land fill site effectively, a plan of operation for the placement of solid waste materials must be prepared. Various operational methods have been developed primarily on the basic of field experience. The method used for land filling are classified as follows

- a) Area method
- b) Trench method
- c) Depression method

2.8.3 Area method

This is used where the soil is not suitable for excavation of trenches, where water table is high or near to surface. The fill operation usually started by building on the earth, with wastes placed in layers and well compacted.

Each layers compacted waste reach a height of 2m to 3m. At the end of each day's operation, a layer of 150 to 300mm of sand is placed on the completed fill as a cover material. The cover material must be hauled in by truck on earth moving equipment e.g. pit chain bulldozer from borrow pit or from where it has been stock piling. Successive lifts are placed on top of one another until it reaches the final design height.

2.8.4 Trench method

This is ideally suitable for an area where there is adequate availability of cover materials at the land fill site, where excavation is possible and where water table is well below the surface. Trench is been dug with bulldozer and the dirt are stock filled to form an embankment behind the first trench.

2.8.5 Depression method

At locations where natural or artificial depression exists, it is often an advantage for effective use for land-filling operation, canyon (deep narrow steep-sided valley), and ravines, dry borrow pits and quarries can be used for this purpose. The techniques to place and compact wastes in depression land fill vary with the geometry of the site, the characteristics of the cover materials, the hydrology of the site and access to the site.

Wet areas such as swamp and marshes total area and ponds, pits from quarries must be land fill sites, special provisions must be made to contain or to eliminate the contamination of local ground water as a result of percolation movement of leachate water and there must be provisions for gases movements. Firstly, this is accomplished by draining the site and then dressing the bottom with clay soil or other appropriate sealant.

2.8.6 Incinerator

Incinerator could be described as a structure constructed for burning of refuse at very high temperature either organic or inorganic waste material, but is very appropriate for burning inorganic waste materials such as paper, cartoons, nylon etc. to mention few.

During burning, most of these materials are lost to the atmosphere where they are oxidized and rendered harmless. The remaining material ash, which is normally of very low size compared with the original material are often remove to ash pits where they could be useful for agricultural purposes. The following are the factors to be considered in the location of incinerator;

- The availability of land
- Type and nature of the solid waste collected from the environment
- The capacity of the waste it can contain at a time
- It is important on the environment

2.8.7 Compositing

Composited refuse is a soil conditioner, which is used especially when the soil structure has deteriorated due to high intensity of rainfall. The anaerobic organisms in the waste generated is allowed to decomposed which makes the refuse to ferment and which in return supply nutrient and humus to the soil.

Also, compositing is a means of reducing volume of waste generated and a means of collecting organic matter, which are used as fertilizer, the process of compositing reduced the volume of refuse more than what incinerator could do.

Some of the factors that affects composite are:

1. If the temperature is rise above 70 °C , degradation is slowed down, i.e., a lower temperature is required for it.

2. Wind lowers the temperature and reduces the moisture on the side of the composite heap.
3. Where there is more than 60% water, the process is slowed down, anaerobic bacterial are stimulated and unpleasant smell are given on.
4. Decomposition of vegetable matter with low carbon or nitrogen garbage.

2.9 Recycling of waste

This is one of the modern ways in which waste can be managed properly. If Ekiti state government can adopt this method of waste disposal then people in Ekiti will see waste as wealth. Recycling waste in Ekiti will provide job opportunity and source of revenue to state government. Useable products and bi-products are obtained by the recycling of solid waste instead of dumping them to decay in dumping site. Waste recycling has started in our industry at small-scale level in production of soap ashes, and the following are also generated from the waste;

- i. Generation of cooking gas (biogas) from vegetable waste (Agricultural Waste)
- ii. Production of gas from waste e.g. methane, carbon dioxide
- iii. Chromium recover from chromium - contain slag
- iv. Utilization by waste tyres for fuel in the industry
- v. Useful organic gases and other aromatic compounds could obtained for Pyroiysis of used syringes, used tyres and other plastic waste e.g. methane, ethylene etc.
- vi. Bone of animals like cow used for glass plate

2.10 Groundwater

Groundwater is the water present beneath Earth's surface in rock and soil_pore_spaces and in the fractures of rock-formations. A unit of rock or an unconsolidated deposit is called an aquifer when it can yield a usable quantity of water. The depth at which soil pore spaces or fractures and voids in rock become completely saturated with water is called the water-table. Groundwater is recharged from the surface; it may discharge from the surface naturally at springs and seeps, and can form oases or wetlands. Groundwater is also often withdrawn for agricultural, municipal, and industrial use by constructing and operating extraction wells. The study of the distribution and movement of groundwater is hydrogeology, also called groundwater hydrology.

2.10.1 Type of tests

Physical Test

- a) Colour
- b) Odour
- c) Turbidity

d) Total solids suspended

e) Appearances

Chemical Test

a) pH

b) Calcium

c) Ammonia

d) Total Hardness

e) iron

Bacterial Test

a) E. Coli

b) Total coliform

These tests will be done on the samples collected and their results collected to know how polluted they are and solution recommended.

2.11 Water quality

For the nation as a whole, the chemical and biological character of ground water is acceptable for most uses. The quality of ground water in some parts of the country, particularly shallow ground water, is changing as a result of human activities. Ground water is less susceptible to bacterial pollution than surface water because the soil and rocks through which ground water flows screen out most of the bacteria. Bacteria, however, occasionally find their way into ground water, sometimes in dangerously high concentrations. But freedom from bacterial pollution alone does not mean that the water is fit to drink. Many unseen dissolved mineral and organic constituents are present in ground water in various concentrations. Most are harmless or even beneficial; though occurring infrequently, others are harmful, and a few may be highly toxic.

Water is a solvent and dissolves minerals from the rocks with which it comes in contact. Ground water may contain dissolved minerals and gases that give it the tangy taste enjoyed by many people. Without these minerals and gases, the water would taste flat. The most common dissolved mineral substances are sodium, calcium, magnesium, potassium, chloride, bicarbonate, and sulfate. In water chemistry, these substances are called common constituents.

Water typically is not considered desirable for drinking if the quantity of dissolved minerals exceeds 1,000 mg/L (milligrams per liter). Water with a few thousand mg/L of dissolved minerals is classed as slightly saline, but it is sometimes used in areas where less-mineralized water is not available. Water from some wells and springs contains very large concentrations of dissolved minerals and cannot be tolerated by humans and other animals or plants. Many parts of the Nation are underlain at depth by highly saline ground water that has only very limited uses. Dissolved mineral constituents can be hazardous to animals or plants in large concentrations; for example, too much sodium in the water may be harmful to people who have heart trouble. Boron is a mineral that is good for plants in small amounts, but is toxic to some plants in only slightly larger concentrations.

Water that contains a lot of calcium and magnesium is said to be hard. The hardness of water is expressed in terms of the amount of calcium carbonate—the principal constituent of limestone—or equivalent minerals that would be formed if the water were evaporated. Water is considered soft if it contains 0 to 60 mg/L of hardness, moderately hard from 61 to 120 mg/L, hard between 121 and 180 mg/L, and very hard if more than 180 mg/L. Very hard water is not desirable for many domestic uses; it will leave a scaly deposit on the inside of pipes, boilers, and tanks. Hard water can be softened at a fairly reasonable cost, but it is not always desirable to remove all the

minerals that make water hard. Extremely soft water is likely to corrode metals, although it is preferred for laundering, dishwashing, and bathing. (Adam, 1998)

2.12 Bacteria and viruses

Over a century of research on naturally-occurring bacteria and their activities allows us to interpret some of the roles of bacteria in ground- water environments. We know that bacteria are found everywhere in our environment. They are common in air, soil, water and in the habitats of our daily lives. Bacteria are commonly present in soil at numbers of about 10^8 - 10^9 cells per gram. Bacterial slime (biofilms) on rocks in streams and rivers may contain 10^9 bacteria per square centimeter. Pristine lake waters contain many thousands of naturally- occurring bacteria per liter. These naturally-occurring bacteria maintain the fertility of soil, they transform minerals and nutrients in water and sediments, and degrade leaf litter and other plant materials producing materials useful to other organisms. In addition, naturally-occurring bacteria carry out activities useful to humans by degrading wastes in our landfills and compost piles, and cleansing water of the pollutants we add. We purposefully use some bacteria to make food (cheese, beer, sauerkraut), we put bacteria to work in sewage treatment plants, and we use them in biotechnology to produce chemicals. Therefore, microbiologists have learned a great deal about the types and activities of naturally-occurring bacteria. Based on principles learned from other environments, we would expect bacteria in ground water to be able to:

- Transform organic carbon to carbon dioxide (CO_2)
- Use up oxygen when sufficient carbon is available for growth
- Transform nitrogen between oxidized (e.g., nitrate - NO_3) and reduced (e.g., ammonium - NH_4 or nitrogen gas - N_2) forms
- Transform iron between oxidized [Fe(III)] and reduced [Fe(II)] forms
- Transform sulfur between oxidized (e.g., sulfate - SO_4) and reduced (e.g., sulfide - H_2S) forms
- Produce methane
- Degrade pesticides, fuels and other organic contaminants
- Affect the distribution and solubility of some metals (e.g., arsenic, uranium, etc.)

Indeed, there is evidence for each of these activities in ground water. The review articles cited above are good resources for more information and case examples. In addition, Norris et al. (1994) provides a general review of the role of bacteria in natural and augmented bioremediation of fuels and solvents in ground water.

Most of the activities of bacteria in ground water are the direct result of the astounding metabolic versatility of bacteria. Although humans and other vertebrate and invertebrate animals are primarily dependent on respiration using oxygen, some bacteria may respire using NO_3 , SO_4 , oxidized (ferric) iron [Fe₃] or a variety of metals (such as arsenic or uranium) as the oxidant. In addition, in the absence of oxygen, bacteria may carry out processes such as methane production or fermentation. Finally, bacteria may be capable of growth on some organic compounds which are toxic to other organisms. The combination of these unique metabolic capabilities suggests that bacteria play important roles in pristine and contaminated ground water environments. Nevertheless, bacteria are limited, as are all living things, by extremes of pH and temperature, by

lack of nutrients to support growth, and by toxicity of some compounds. In addition, bacteria are subject to predation by larger microorganisms, such as protozoa. Each of these environmental features must be assessed when interpreting the role of bacteria in a particular ground water process. (Adam, 1998)

Fig 2.1: Well far from the dumpsite (sample B)

Fig 2.2: Well close to the dumpsite (sample A)

Fig 2.3: Selected dumpsite at Iworoko-Ekiti.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Composition of the solid waste at dumpsite.

3.1.1 Sampling of materials.

Solid waste sample was used for the investigation. Heaps of waste was taken in a selected dumpsite at Iworoko-Ekiti using a shovel into polythene nylon and it was used to convey the solid waste sample down to the laboratory for the analysis. The dumpsite is situated beside an uncompleted building within a residential area, it comprises of different kinds of wastes with bush around it, it is a kind of dumpsite that accommodates goats, lizards, mice and rats and it is a dumpsite that is improperly disposed, not managed well.

3.1.2 Determination of the solid waste composition on dumpsite using quarter method.

Aim: To determine waste composition at dump site.

Apparatus: Shovel, Hand gloves, Head pan and a weighing machine.

Procedures:

- Waste sampling was carried out.
- The sampled waste was measured with weighing machine.
- The weighed sampled waste heap was divided into four equal parts, ABCD, values was confirmed by the weighing machine.
- A part of the divided waste heaps was divided into four equal parts.
- A subdivision of this waste heap was sorted out with hands covered with hand gloves into different kinds of waste found in it to know its composition e.g. decomposed food, nylon, can, plastic, wood, etc.
- After the above step was done, each kind of waste was weighed with weighing machine to know their weight in kg.
- To determine the percentage by weight of the composition of the solid, the weight (kg) of each of the composition of the solid waste subdivision was divided by the total weight (kg) of the selected subdivision multiplied by 100. For example, if weight of the selected subdivision is 100kg and one of the composition is weighing 20kg, the percentage of the composition will be, $\frac{20}{100} \times 100 = 20\%$ (Rojas-Valencia and Najera-Aguilar, (2012))

3.2 Water quality tests

3.2.1 Sampling of materials

Water sample was used for this investigation. The groundwater samples was collected for analysis from two wells in Iworoko-Ekiti, one well of distance 10m to the dumpsite and the other, 51.3m to the dumpsite for accurate analyses, the well far from the dumpsite is 20.4m deep, well kept with cover on the top of the well and it has a neat environment and the well close to the dump is 20m deep, not in a good condition, it does not have a proper cover on it but planks of wood serving as the cover and the environment around is bushy with some part of the dumpsite/waste around it.

After collection, the samples was stored in well-drained clean polyethylene bottles already rinsed out with the same water samples in each case and the temperature was measured immediately. The measuring of their various temperatures immediately after collection is very important. Two litres was collected from each of the wells for each of the analyses (physical, chemical and bacteriological) and stored, bacteriological analysis was done within twenty four hours after collection to prevent multiplication of the bacteria. APHA method of examination will be adopted.

3.2.2 Tests procedures

The following tests are to be performed on each of the samples;

- | | |
|--------------------|-----------------------------|
| (A) Physical tests | (1) pH |
| (1) Colour | (2) Ammonia (mg/L) |
| (2) Odour | (3) Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L) |
| (3) Total Solid | (4) Total hardness (mg/L) |
| (4) Appearance | (5) Iron (mg/L) |
| (5) Turbidity | (6) Calcium (mg/L) |
| (6) Temperature | (C) Bacteriological test |
| (B) Chemical tests | (1) Ecoli |

3.2.2.1 Physical tests

1. Determination of temperature.

Aims: To determine the temperature of the samples.

Apparatus: Thermometer.

Procedures:

- The temperature of the water samples was taken at the point of collection, using a glass thermometer. It is measured in degree Celsius (°C).
- The thermometer was dipped into the samples and the level of mercury in the thermometer was monitored until it is constant i.e. stationary.
- The stationary point on the thermometer was read and taken as the temperature of water.

2. Determination of colour.

Aims: To determine the colour of the water samples

Apparatus: Colour comparator, clean test tubes, disc: NSA & nesters 50

Procedures:

- The test tube was filled with 50ml of the water sample and another test tube with distilled water was placed on the left hand.
- The text tube containing the raw water was placed on the right hand.
- The graduated disc on the apparition (while facing north daylight) was rotated until the colour of the two test tube seen and identified i.e. until it matches the colour of the two samples, the value on the apparatus at which these colours matches was taken as the colour in HAZEN SCALE.

3. Determination of appearance.

Aim: To determine the appearance of the samples.

Apparatus: Clean test tubes, test tube holder.

Procedures:

- A clean test tube was filled with the water sample.
- The test tube was placed in the test tube holder and viewed while facing north day light. This tells us if the water is clear or not.

4. Determination of turbidity

Aim: To determine how turbid the water samples are.

Apparatus: Test tube, turbid meter, light shield.

Procedures:

- A dry turbid meter (H.F. instrument LTD, Canada) was calibrated according to the manufacturer's instruction; this was done by first putting the meter to 0.02 N.T.U

standards into the optical well. Covered with the light shield, the range knob was adjusted until 0.02 N.T.U standard was displayed on it.

- After displaying on it, the optical well was immediately replaced with the tube filled with the water sample and then covered with the light shield.
- The value which appeared on the turbid meter after setting the range value was taken as the turbidity of the samples, expressed in N.T.U. (nephelometric turbidity unit).

5. Determination of total solid.

Aim: To determine the total solid in the samples.

Apparatus: Desiccators, evaporating dish, heater, digital weighing and scale dish carrier.

Procedures:

- The empty evaporated dish was first measured and the weight recorded
- Then, 50ml of the sample was measured into the pre-weighted dish and heated to dryness. After then, the dish cooled in the desiccators.
- The final weight of the dish after cooling was taken and value recorded.
- The value of the initial weight of dish was deducted from the value of the final weight of the dish multiplied by 1000mg, to know the value of the total solid i.e., $(F-I) \times 1000\text{mg}$

6. Determination of odour.

Aim: To know if the water samples have odour or not.

Apparatus: Sample bottle, constant temperature bat, odour flasks, pipette and thermometer.

Procedures:

- The volume of odourless water was placed in flask then the sample was pipette into the water and mixed.
- A separate flask containing only odourless water was used as the reference for comparison.
- Heat was applied to the dilutions and the reference water to temperature desired for running the test.
- The flask containing odourless water was shook, the stopper was removed and the vapour was snuffed. The dilutions vapour was snuffed also, and then the difference was observed.

7. Determination of conductivity

Aim: To know whether the water samples have electric conductivity or not.

Apparatus: Test tubes and Jenway conductivity meter (4510 model).

Procedure:

- The probe was dipped into the container of the well water samples until a stable reading was obtained and recorded.

3.2.2.1 Chemical Tests

1. Determination of pH

Aim: To determine the pH value of the water samples.

Apparatus: pH meter, pH and reference electrodes, glass ware, pH petrifly, water Sample, pH paper indicator (universal).

Procedures:

- The beaker was filled with water sample.
- The pH meter was standardized with buffer solutions of pH.
- The pH electrode was allowed to stand before dipping it into the water sample, and then the reading was taken.

2. Determination of Dissolved Oxygen

Aim: To determine the level of dissolved oxygen in the samples.

Apparatus: Digital oxygen meter, magnetic stirrer, sodium sulphide solution, beakers. Procedures:

- The polagraphic digital oxygen electrode was first calibrated with sodium sulphide solution by stirring using magnetic stirrer to make the electrode effective for 30mins.
- The water sample was measured into 100ml sampling beaker.
- The calibrated electrode was inserted into it and the instrument powered.
- The displayed reading after the operation was taken as the dissolved oxygen reading in mg/L.

3. Determination of Total Hardness

Aim: To determine the hardness level of the samples.

Apparatus: Calibrated shaker bottle, total hardness tablets, clean glass stirring rod. Procedures:

- 50ml of the sample was measured into the calibrated shaker bottle.
- The total hardness tablets crushed was mixed with a stirring rod into the sample.
- The mixture was shook with the addition of this tablet one at a time until the colour change from plum red to blue.
- The calculation for total hardness of the sample in mg/l was done using the formula below.

$$\text{Total hardness} = (\text{no of tables} \times 40) - 20$$

- The result gotten was compared with the ranges given;

0 - 50 = Soft

50 -100 = moderately soft

100- 150 = slightly hard

150- 200 = moderately hard

4. Determination of iron

Aim: To determine the iron concentration of the samples.

Apparatus: Colour disc, comparator, 10ml mould cell

Procedures:

- The appropriate disc (i.e. 3/117) was fitted into comparator.
- The 13.5mm/10ml moulded cell containing the sample was placed in the left hand compartment of the comparator.
- A similar cell was rinsed with the sample and was filled with 10ml of the sample.
- An iron HR tablet was crushed and added to the sample, it was mixed till the tablet dissolved.
- The cell was placed in the right hand compartment of the compactor.
- The colour was matched by holding the comparator up to north day light and the disc was turned until the match was found. The figure showing in the bottom right hand corner represents mg/l of iron present in the sample.

5. Determination of calcium.

Aim: To determine the calcium concentration of the samples.

Apparatus: Burette, retort stand, murexide/NaCl, indicator, EDTA (ethylene Diamine tetra-acetic acid), conical flasks, spatula, sodium hydroxide, test tube.

Procedures:

- 50ml of the sample was measured into a conical flask.
- 2ml of sodium hydroxide was added to and MUREXIDE indicator.
- EDTA was added from the burette to the conical flask until the indicator changes colour, indicating that the end point has been reached. The volume of EDTA used was recorded.
- The steps above were repeated until three concordant titres are obtained
- The average of these concordant titres was then used to calculate the concentration of calcium ions in the water sample.
- Calculation: $\text{Calcium (mg/L)} = \frac{\text{EDTA concentration (mol l/L)} \times \text{volume of EDTA used(L)}}{\text{volume of water sample(L)}}$

6. Determination of ammonia

Aim: To determine the ammonia concentration of the samples

Apparatus: Comparator, molded cells and ammonia tablets.

Procedures:

- Disc 3/113 was fitted into the comparator.
- Two 13.5 mm/100ml molded cells were filled to the 10ml mark with sample and one cell was placed in the left hand compartment of the comparator.
- Ammonia No.1 tablet crushed added to it. It was consciously mixed until both tablets were dissolved. The cell was placed in the right hand side of the comparator and was allowed to stand for 10 minutes.
- After standing for the required time, colour was matched against the standard by holding the comparator up to north day light and turning the disc until the correct match was found. The figure shown in the bottom right hand corner represented the value of the ammonia presented in the water sample in mg/l.

3.2.2.2 Bacteriological Tests

1. Determination of E.Coli and Other Bacteria

Aim: To determine the presence of E coli in the water

Apparatus: Plastic Petri- dishes, test tube, pipette, 500ml conical flask, aluminium foil, stirring rod, cotton wool, 98% ethanol, Colony counter, microscope, autoclave(Sterilizer).

Reagents: EMB-ARGAR (eosin methylene blue) agar, stains and indicator. EMB (Eosin Methylene Blue) agar is a selective media on which the water indicator of Escherichia coli can grow. It forms a blue sheen on it. Temperature is used to determine pathogenic strain of E. Coli, E. Coli will grow at a temperature of 44°C while on pathogenic, E coli cannot survive beyond 37°C.

Procedures;

Washing & Sterilization of Materials:

Petri - dishes, test tubes, pipettes, conical flask(500ml) and stirring rod was washed with soap and rinsed with tap water and distilled water and then dried in the oven at a temperature range 160°C for 2 hrs; after this, the Petri- dishes was sterilized using the oven.

Incubation:

The samples was poured into two Petri-dishes, labelled A & B (two samples), EMB-ARGAR (eosin methylene blue) agar, stains and indicator was poured into the samples and stirred together then put in the incubator for 18hrs at 37°C, this temperature allowed the growth of bacteria and it was kept at constant.

Plate Count:

This is the process of counting the colonies which appeared on the plates. This will be done by viewing the plate through a microscope to see the various colonies easily and counting them with the colony counter.

(Abimbola et al, 2005), Cheesbrough (2000), Christensen et al (2000), and Hie (2005))

TABLE 3.1: ACCEPTABLE ALLOWABLE CONCENTRATION OF CHEMICAL SUBSTANCES AND PROPERTIES AFFECTING POTABILITY.

Nature of sample	NAFDAC	WHO(standard permissible)	Desirable
Temperature	–	40	–
pH value	6.5 – 8.5	6.5 – 9.2	7.0 – 8.5
Turbidity (N.T.U)	–	25	5
Colour (hazen unit)	–	–	–
Odour	–	–	–
Dissolved solid (mg/l)	500	500	200
Appearance	–	–	–
Total solid (mg/l)	–	1500	500
Chloride (mg/l)	200	600	200
Iron (mg/l)	–	1.0	0.3
Phosphate	–	–	–
Hardness (mg/l)	–	300	200
Dissolved oxygen	–	–	–
Calcium	–	–	–
Nitrate	–	100	45
Suspended solid	–	–	–
Bicarbonate	–	–	–
Alkalinity	100	120	80
Biochemical oxygen	0.3	6	–
Total E coli counts	–	–	–

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FIG. 4.1 Result on the composition of the solid waste at dumpsite

Source: Field Analysis (2022)

4.2 Discussion

Municipal solid waste contains a wide variety of materials, some can be burnt, others cannot, some can be recovered and recycled, and others cannot. If the management option is only to dispose the waste materials, then the composition does not matter. However, most federal or governmental regulation in the developed countries require that all possible options of effective waste management should be considered; and thus not only disposal option, because of this, identifying the specific components of waste materials (stream) is an important step for setting waste management goals and the waste composition can also influence the type of contamination found in the water samples. (Tchobanoglous et al, 1998)

The following are the ways to process solid waste;

- (1) Incineration: it is one of the most effective method of reducing the volume and weight of municipal solid waste. It involves burning municipal solid waste in properly designed furnace under suitable temperature and operating conditions. It is a chemical process in which the combustible portion of waste is combined with oxygen, forming mostly carbon dioxide and water. The chemical reaction called oxidation, releases heat which is a thermal energy. The CO_2 and H_2O are usually released into the atmosphere. Incineration can reduce municipal refuse by about 90% in volume and 75% in weight. In densely populated urban areas, where large sites suitable for sanitary land filling are not available within reasonable handling distances, incineration may be the most economical option for refuse processing. In many cases, it is feasible to design and operate the incinerator so that the heat from combustion can be recovered and used to produce electricity or steam; this type of system is often called a resource recovery or waste-to-energy facility.

- (2) **Pyrolysis:** Pyrolysis is a high-temperature thermal process that can provide alternative to incineration as it taken place in a low oxygen or oxygen free environment and produced product that can be used as fuels. Natural gas is burned to start the process instead of oxidation, a complex series of decomposition and other chemical reaction takes place. Air pollution is less compares to incineration owing to less waste gases. It can be used for processing discarded rubber tyres as it reduces them to oil and methane gas.
- (3) **Shredding and pulverizing:** Size reduction of municipal solid waste is accomplished by the physical processes of shredding and pulverizing. These two physical processes reduce sizes of both individual components and can reduce the overall volume of original or raw waste material by as 40%. Shredding refers to the actions of cutting and tearing, whereas pulverizing refers to actions of crushing and grinding. Apart from the benefit of overall volume reduction, the size reduction through this method is needed in the preparation of refuse-derived fuel in incineration and composting. The size reduction also reduces the performance of the mechanical separation machinery. In addition, shredding of refuse prior to land burial or land fill can increase the capacity of the land fill and also reduces the potential of rodent infestation. The most common equipment used for this processing is the Hammer Mills.
- (4) **Baling:** this is the compaction of solid waste into the form of rectangular blocks or bales. The municipal solid waste bales are typically about 1.5m² in size and approximately 1 tonne in weight. Solid waste can be compacted under high pressures in either vertical or horizontal presses, and the bales are frequently wrapped with steel wire to help retain their rectangular shape during handling. The percent volume reduction is expressed as:

$$\text{Volume reduction (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Initial Volume} - \text{Final Volume})}{(\text{Initial Volume})}$$

$$\text{Compaction ratio} = \frac{(\text{Initial Volume})}{(\text{Final Volume})}$$

- (5) **Composting:** Composting is the process in which are the organic portion of municipal solid waste is allowed to decompose under carefully controlled conditions. The transformation and the decomposition of the waste are accomplished by the action of bacteria, fungi and other microorganisms with proper control of moisture, temperature and aeration. In addition, composting can stabilize the waste and produce an end product that may be recycled for beneficial use. The end product is called compost and it may be used as a soil conditioner. Composting can increase the organic and nutrient content of soil and improve the texture and ability to retain moisture. However, the demand for compost is low because of its poor quality as fertilizer, cost of transporting it and the availability and ease of applying inorganic chemical fertilizers. (Tchobanoglous et al, 1998)

4.3 Water quality analysis results

Results of the water quality carried out on the water samples from the wells from different locations of distances 10m and 51.5m from the dumpsite are presented in Table 2 of chapter 4. The W.H.O. standard of drinking water was used as the baseline to compare the water quality from the sources.

Table 4.1 Water samples result of the selected wells

S/N	PARAMETERS	SAMPLE A (10m away)	SAMPLE B (51.3m away)	W.H.O LIMIT
1	Colour	10.0 TCU	5.0 TCU	5.0
2	Appearance	Not clear	Not clear	Clear
3	Taste	Objectionable	Objectionable	Unobjectionable
4	Odour	Objectionable	Objectionable	Unobjectionable
5	Conductivity	719 μ s/cm	711 μ s/cm	1000 μ s/cm
6	Turbidity	6.00 N.T.U.	3.00 N.T.U.	5 N.T.U.
7	pH	5.2 (Acidic)	6.42 (Acidic)	6.5-8.5
8	Temperature	25.8°C	26.3°C	None
9	Total alkalinity	81.37mg/L	71.26mg/L	150mg/L
10	Total hardness	53.4mg/L	37.51mg/L	100mg/L
11	Total suspended solid	13.17mg/L	4.23mg/L	500mg/L
12	Total dissolved solid	691mg/L	687mg/L	500mg/L
13	Total solid	704.17mg/L	691.23mg/L	1500mg/L
14	Iron	1.20mg/L	0.31mg/L	0.3mg/L
15	Dissolved oxygen	7.13mg/L	9.27mg/L	None
16	Calcium	41.7mg/L	31.10mg/L	150mg/L
17	E coli	+ve (22.68x10 ²)	+ve (10.08x10 ²)	-ve

Source: Field analysis (2022)

FIG. 4.2 Hydrochemical results of the selected wells

4.4 Discussion

As it can be seen from Table 4.1 and FIG. 4.2, it is obvious that the concentration of physical, chemical and biological parameter of the water in the wells decreases with increase in distances from the point of waste deposit (dumpsite).

These figures clearly compliment the observation and the trend of the waste parameters in the table, it shows natural attenuation of the concentration of the physical, chemical and biological constituents of the wells, these observations would have been caused by sedimentation, dilution, dispersion and sunlight.

It is well known that a periodic check of the well pollution level for a period not less than 10 years would be adequate for good analysis toward future development and environment usage of the wells. However, observation from the result of the test on the water could also give a considerate indication of the pollution level of the well. In this study, reference will be made to the revised international standard for drinking water by the world health organization (W.H.O.) 2001, which is included in Table 1, chapter 4.

4.4.1 Appearance and colour

The desirable limit for colour of a potable water is 5 unit, with the highest permissible at 20 units. The value obtained for the well close to the dumpsite is quite high when compared with W.H.O. standard. The reason is that the well is very close to the dumping site but for the well that is far from the dumpsite, the value obtained is the same with W.H.O. standard reason been that colour decreases with distance from the source of pollution.

4.4.2 Turbidity

High values of turbidity which resulted in high colour value can attributed to the sediments and suspended solid especially during high discharge values from month July. Though safe limit of turbidity could not be categorically ascertained but little sedimentation process could put the level of this physical characteristic under a desirable control. This is evident in the decrease in turbidity with distance away from the point of pollution. Sedimentation is the process of causing heavier solid particles in suspension, both organic and inorganic to settle by retaining water in a basin. When the process is carried out without the aid of coagulants, it is called plain sedimentation and when with coagulants is called sedimentation with coagulation.

4.4.3 Acidity

The pH values of the well water samples are shown in Table 4.1, which their values did not fall within the safe limits of the W.H.O. standard (6.5-8.5) but according to the W.H.O. guidelines, the values of the pH has no effect on the drinking water quality of the water. It also shows that they are mildly acidic, acidity increases the capacity of water to attack geological materials making it potentially harmful for human drinking, this can be treated by the application of lime, thus the moderate acidity of these water samples suggest that the water samples were susceptible to some degree of trace metal pollution, possibly present in the rock matrix through which the water percolates and the low pH value might be due to the materials used in the construction of the wells and soil types. The soils might have low level of dissolved CO₂ and HCO₃, which lowered the pH of groundwater. But however, pH value increase with increase in distance of the well from the pollution source. (W.H.O. 2006)

4.4.4 Suspended solids

High levels of dissolved or suspended solids are among the most common complaints from water well and spring owners. Sediment can originate from a poorly developed well, nearby land use, or an aging well while dissolved solids are often caused by natural dissolution of minerals or polluting activities. Most raw wastes have suspended solid content of 200mg/l and above. High values of suspended solids and dissolved solids in tropical countries are as a result of vegetation cover and other activities around the wells. The suspended solids in the river decreases with distance from the waste dumpsite. But this can be treated using sedimentation process, which is the settling of sludge and separation of sludge from the affluent.

4.4.5 Total solid (TS)

Value as high as 1500mg/l which are cumulative values from dissolved, colloidal and suspended solids. This is the maximum limit permitted by the WHO standard. However, this value is not permissible for potable water, which is used for drinking. It can be easily removed with the process of sedimentation. The total solids of the water samples from the wells are within the acceptable level recommended by W.H.O.; however the total solids decreased with increase in distance to the pollution source. The reason for this behaviour is the physical processes of sedimentation, dilution and dispersion which occur in the wells and total solids can also be treated using chlorination, which is the application of small quantities of chlorine or chlorine compound to the water.

4.4.6 Alkalinity

Total alkalinity value of the well water samples are expressed as the acid neutralizing ability of the water and are determined by how much carbonate, bicarbonate and hydroxide present. Excess alkalinity results to a distinct flat and unpleasant taste of the water. From Table 4.1, the alkalinity of the well water samples fall within the W.H.O. limits allowed for drinkable water.

The primary source of natural alkalinity is carbondioxide in the atmosphere and in soil gases that dissolves in rain, surface water, and groundwater. Bicarbonate released through dissolution of carbonate minerals also contributes to alkalinity. Major contaminant sources of alkalinity include landfills and other sites where alkaline or basic chemicals have been dumped. High levels of alkalinity may be accompanied by objectionable taste, or precipitation of scale in pipes and containers.

4.4.7 Calcium

It is an essential ingredient to the human diet; thus, its presence in drinking water could be beneficial to a level of 75 to 200mg/L. The desirable level of calcium in the wells may be due to the geomorphology of the wells, and also content of calcium decreases with increase of distance of the well to the pollution source. This is likely due to dilution of water along the well strata.

Calcium is a necessary nutrient to ensure strong bones and teeth. There are no health effects of calcium in drinking water but it is a primary cause of hardness in water and results in the formation of scale in plumbing and water containers. Calcium concentrations do not limit groundwater use for irrigation. Therefore, there is no need for the treatment of calcium in this study because of its benefits.

4.4.8 Iron

If the standard level of iron for potable water is 1.0mg/l, a critical value of 1.8mg/l could be acceptable for an untreated well even as a source of water supply. The value could be due to reduction in oxidation process within the water to convert it to perceptible iron II oxide. The iron content in the well far from the dumpsite is within the W.H.O. standard but the well close to the dumpsite have value greater than the highest permissible level recommended for drinking water by W.H.O., possible source is from the decomposition of organic matter, weathering and dissolution process resulting in production of iron oxide. Sediment filter, carbon filter, or water softeners can remove small amounts of iron. Distillation or reverse osmosis can also remove any type of iron. (Department of health, Minnesota and Abimbola et al, 2005)

4.4.9 Dissolved oxygen (DO)

There are numerous components that can be found in drinking water, one of which is dissolved oxygen. The dissolved oxygen in water is the total amount of oxygen that has already been dissolved in a water sample. When dissolved oxygen is at the right concentration, aquatic ecosystems can thrive. On the other hand, too little dissolved oxygen means that aquatic species might not have enough dissolved oxygen to survive. When it comes to drinking water, relatively high levels of dissolved oxygen can lead to a better taste. Bodies of water obtain oxygen directly from the atmosphere as well as from aquatic plants. In the event that dissolved oxygen levels

have dropped precipitously in a body of water, the entire ecosystem could suffer. Keep in mind that running water results in more oxygen being dissolved when compared to still water that's found in a lake or pond.

4.4.10 Total hardness

The results of hardness parameter analyzed for the well water samples shown in Table 4.1 are relatively soft according to W.H.O. standard. (W.H.O. 2006)

4.4.11 Conductivity

The conductivity of the well water samples in Table 4.1 are all within the W.H.O. acceptable limits. The electrical conductivity in the samples is 719 and 711 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$. Generally, the electrical conductivity is affected by the geology of the area through which the water flows. It is a function of magnesium, calcium, sodium and sulphate in the water. (Okereke et al, 2014)

4.4.12 Temperature

The temperature of well water samples are 25.8°C and 26.3°C. The temperature range observed in this study will discourage the rate of chemical and biological reactions, solubility of gases in the water which could impact negatively on the taste and odor of the water. (Aribisala et al, 2017)

4.4.13 Total Coliform and E coli

The W.H.O. acceptable limits for total coliform and E coli for drinkable water quality is 0.0mg/L, but according to the results gotten in Table 4.1, the well water samples characteristics of coliform and E coli exceeded the W.H.O. limits, sample A is 22.68×10^2 cfu while sample B is 10.08×10^2 cfu i.e, there is presence of microbial faecal contamination. Presence of faecal coli in the samples show pollution of the water by human defecation and taking a close look at the results, the faecal contamination varies with change in distance of the well from the dumpsite.

Coliform or E coli can be treated in water by the use of chlorine. Chemical dosing pumps are often used to inject chlorine into drinking water sources, which then acts as a disinfectant that kills the bacteria.

While chlorine is considered an effective treatment for E coli, there are two standard water filters used to handle this issue. The first type is reverse osmosis systems which are highly efficient in removing E coli from drinking water. Reverse osmosis is a water purification process that uses a semi-permeable membrane (synthetic lining) to filter out unwanted molecules and large particles. These reverse osmosis systems utilize filtration membranes that force water through the membrane, while not allowing pollutants such as E coli to pass through. UV systems are usually needed as a second source of filtration due to reverse osmosis systems being unable to effectively remove all E coli from drinking water. UV systems have attained their reputation as the most effective and affordable water treatment solution in eradicating bacteria through high intensity radiation. As water passes through the UV system, it is hit with ultraviolet rays which kill all existing bacteria in the water. (Ibiang et al, 2016 and Pure aqua, Inc, 2020)

Fig 4.1: Chemical dosing pump

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study has provided data on the level of physiochemical and bacteriological properties of well water in Iworoko-Ekiti, Ekiti state. This study was set out to compare the values of the properties from each source selected with W.H.O. standard for drinking water. Considering the results obtained from the investigation in the previous chapter, the following was noticed;

- 1) Total hardness of water samples from the study area was found to be within the limits of 0-150mg/L specified by W.H.O. standard, therefore making the water samples soft.
- 2) The total coliform and E coli of the well water samples exceeded the W.H.O. standard limit.
- 3) The pH of the well water samples was slightly acidic and it didn't fall between W.H.O. standard limit for drinking water
- 4) The total solids were found to be within reasonable allowable limit recommended by W.H.O.
- 5) The appearance, colour, taste and odour of the well water samples are all objectionable.
- 6) Other chemical parameters of the well water samples met the W.H.O. acceptable limit for drinkingwater.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results obtained from the previous chapter or from the analysis conducted in the study on the well water samples in Iworoko-Ekiti, Ekiti state, the following recommendations were made;

- 1) It is recommended that regular laboratory tests should be conducted on water samples from different water sources to ensure that the quality meet with the required standard by W.H.O. and NAFDAC.
- 2) It is recommended that the wells in the area selected for analysis should be treated against acidic water, which is treated by liming. Ground limestone is used to raise the pH of water.
- 3) It is recommended that the wells in the area selected for analysis should be treated for E coli by boiling the water before use, application of chlorine to the wells affected by using chemical dosing pump and use of advance forms of treatment; reverse osmosis systems and UV systems.

- 4) It is recommended that the state government should construct a proper landfill for the disposal of waste generated in the area.
- 5) It is recommended that the occupants of the area should make use of other means of waste disposal, e.g, burning of waste, recycling and reusing of waste; a plastic waste can be used for other means rather than its original use, etc.
- 6) It is recommended that the existing dumpsite be removed or properly managed.

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